

A Sensor-Driven Framework for Modeling the Impact of Metro Crowding Contributions on Local Thermal Stress Across Transit-Oriented Development Zones

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Abstract

Urban metro systems, in rapidly developing cities like Delhi, experience high levels of passenger crowding, which may contribute to localized thermal stress within Transit-Oriented Development zones. This study examines the effect of metro crowding on local thermal conditions using a regression model, where Land Surface Temperature is modeled as the dependent variable, and the Crowding Contribution Index, developed from Automated Fare Collection and General Transit Feed Specification data, serves as the key independent variable. To account for ecological moderation, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index and Normalized Difference Moisture Index are included. Data from 237 stations across the Delhi Metro network were analyzed using regression across three concentric Transit-Oriented Development buffer zones: 0–500 meters, 500–800 meters, and 800–2000 meters. In the 0–500 meter and 500–800 meter zones, the Crowding Contribution Index is positively associated with Land Surface Temperature, indicating that stations with high crowding contribute to localized thermal hotspots, while the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index and Normalized Difference Moisture Index mitigate these effects through vegetative cooling and surface moisture. In contrast, in the 800–2000 meter buffer zone, Land Surface Temperature is influenced predominantly by ecological variables, with no significant effect of crowding. This study demonstrates how sensor-enabled transit datasets, spatial analytics, and geospatial sensing can be integrated into intelligent mobility frameworks to model urban heat impacts. It highlights the need for climate-responsive, sensor-informed transit planning that links environmental performance with passenger dynamics, supporting the development of future-ready transportation networks in megacities.

Keywords: Land Surface Temperature; Transit-Oriented Development; Normalized Difference Moisture Index; Normalized Difference Vegetation Index; Sensor-Enabled Transit Data

1 Introduction

Urbanization continues to be a key driver of environmental change in rapidly growing cities, where the conversion of vegetation and agricultural land into impervious built-up areas leads to higher land surface temperatures and intensifies the Heat Island effect [1], [2], [3], [4]. In response to the environmental and spatial challenges of rapid urban expansion, urban sprawl, and increasing automobile dependency, Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) has emerged as a prominent strategic urban planning approach [5]. TOD emphasizes compact, high-density, and mixed-use development concentrated within walkable distances typically 500 to 800 meters from public transit stations, with the goal of promoting sustainable mobility and reducing dependence on private vehicles [6]. By integrating land use with transportation infrastructure, Transit-Oriented Development aims to reduce car dependency, increase public transit ridership, and promote more sustainable and livable urban environments [7], [8]. Recent studies have begun to explore how urban rail infrastructure contributes to localized land surface temperature (LST) increases, exacerbating the urban heat island effect [9].

Metro stations, due to their high commuter volumes, intensified land use, and proliferation of impervious surfaces, often function as micro-urban cores characterized by elevated anthropogenic heat emissions [10]. Yet, within this framework, the role of passenger crowding, a fundamental operational challenge in mass transit systems, has remained largely overlooked as a potential contributor to thermal stress in TOD zones.

For addressing this critical gap, this study uses the Crowding Contribution Index (CCI), a spatially explicit metric developed in prior work using Automated Fare Collection (AFC) and General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data. The CCI quantifies each station's contribution to link-level in-vehicle crowding and captures spatial variations in crowding intensity across the metro network. Traditionally, crowding has been examined through the lens of service quality, user discomfort, or operational efficiency [11], [12]. Notably, [13] demonstrated that overcrowding in Ahmedabad's bus system resulted in significant social and environmental costs, including reduced fuel efficiency and increased pollutant exposure. By linking sensor-derived passenger dynamics with satellite-observed environmental variables, this study models the effect of crowding on LST within

1 TOD zones. The present approach integrates core
2 principles of intelligent transportation systems by
3 combining data-driven modeling, geospatial
4 environmental sensing, and spatial analytics to inform the
5 design of adaptive and climate-resilient transit
6 infrastructure [14]. This framework enables a nuanced
7 understanding of the interactions between passenger
8 dynamics and environmental stressors, thereby
9 supporting evidence-based strategies for sustainable
10 urban mobility planning

11
12 Their findings underscore the broader externalities of
13 crowding beyond passenger experience, warranting
14 policy interventions that integrate operational and
15 environmental considerations.

16
17 Building on this perspective, our study explores
18 whether higher crowding as measured by the CCI
19 correlates with elevated LST in TOD environments. In
20 doing so, we shift the discourse from crowding as an
21 operational burden to crowding as an environmental
22 externality with potential implications for climate
23 resilience. To account for ecological mediation effects,
24 we also incorporate the Normalized Difference
25 Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalized Difference
26 Moisture Index (NDMI) two widely used remote sensing
27 proxies representing vegetation cover and surface
28 moisture, respectively. NDVI has been extensively
29 validated as an indicator of vegetative cooling capacity
30 [15], while NDMI reflects evapotranspiration potential, a
31 critical regulator of surface heat[16]. Including these
32 indices enables a more comprehensive analysis of the
33 interaction between anthropogenic crowding pressures
34 and natural environmental buffers.

35
36 This study contributes to the growing literature on
37 climate-sensitive transit planning and provides new
38 insights into how mobility-related stressors intersect with
39 urban heat dynamics. By bridging crowding analysis with
40 environmental metrics, our research offers a
41 multidimensional approach to TOD design, one that
42 integrates ecological considerations with transit
43 efficiency to enhance thermal resilience in urban
44 environments.

45 46 **2 Data and Methodology**

47 48 **2.1 Study Area**

49
50 This research is based on the Delhi Metro network,
51 situated in India's capital, one of Southern Asia's most
52 thickly populated and rapidly urbanizing regions. The
53 Delhi Metro has evolved into the principal public
54 transport backbone, with over 390 kilometers of
55 operational routes and 288 stations spanning multiple
56 corridors. The system extends into the wider National
57 Capital Region (NCR), connecting urban centers such as
58 Gurugram, Noida, Faridabad, and Ghaziabad. For this

study, data from 237 stations managed by the Delhi Metro
Rail Corporation (DMRC) for the year 2023 were analyzed,
covering key lines including Yellow, Red, Blue, Violet,
Green, Magenta, Grey, and the Airport Express. Given its
extensive ridership and central role in shaping urban form,
the Delhi Metro provides a representative context for
examining the interplay between transit crowding and
thermal environmental outcomes within Transit-Oriented
Development buffer zones.

59 60 **2.2 Data Sources**

61
62 This study integrates three primary data sources metro
63 operational data, satellite-derived environmental
64 indicators, and spatial buffers to evaluate the relationship
65 between transit crowding and localized thermal conditions
across the Delhi Metro system. The Crowding
Contribution Index is a novel metric developed in the
author's prior work to quantify the directional contribution
of individual metro stations to in-vehicle crowding at the
link level. This index leverages granular passenger flow
data from Automated Fare Collection (AFC) systems
comprising smart card tap-in and tap-out records with
General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data, which
provide real-time service attributes such as vehicle
frequency, capacity, and dwell times. The mean LST was
estimated from Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI)
and Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) data for the year 2023,
sourced via the United States Geological Survey (USGS).
The mono-window algorithm was applied to retrieve LST
values, which were subsequently averaged at the station
level across three concentric Transit-Oriented
Development buffer zones: 0–500 m (core TOD), 500–
800 m (transition TOD), and 800–2000 m (non-
TOD/peripheral). This spatial framework enables the
capture of localized thermal gradients as a function of
distance from transit hubs. Two key environmental indices,
NDVI and NDMI were extracted from the same Landsat 8
imagery. NDVI, derived from the near-infrared (NIR) and
red spectral bands, serves as a proxy for vegetative density
and canopy coverage. NDMI, calculated using NIR and
shortwave infrared (SWIR) bands, reflects surface
moisture content and evapotranspiration potential. Both
indices were computed using ArcGIS Pro and spatially
averaged within each of the defined TOD buffer zones.
These variables serve to isolate and control ecological
influences on thermal variation in regression models.

NDVI (Vegetation Index)

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

High NDVI values (0.3 to 0.8): Dense, healthy green
vegetation. Moderate NDVI (0.1 to 0.3): Sparse vegetation
or shrubs. Low or negative NDVI (< 0.1): Urban/built-up
surfaces, bare soil, or water bodies.

1 NDMI (Moisture Index)

$$2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \quad 5 \quad NDMI = \frac{NIR - SWIR}{NIR + SWIR}$$

6 Low/Negative NDMI (< 0): Dry vegetation, impervious urban surfaces

7
8 This study employs four variables CCI, LST, NDVI, and
9 NDVI for assessing the association amid metro crowding
10 and localized thermal conditions across TOD zones. To
11 capture spatial heterogeneity, separate values for LST,
12 NDVI, and NDMI were calculated for 0–500 m, 500–
13 800 m, and 800–2000 m buffers around each station. The
14 delineation of TOD buffer zones in this study 0–500 m
15 (TOD zone), 500–800 m (transition), and 800–2000 m
16 (peripheral) is based on spatial thresholds recommended
17 in the National TOD Policy by the Ministry of Housing
18 and Urban Affairs (MoHUA, 2017) and adopted in the
19 Master Plan for Delhi 2041 (DDA, 2021).
20

21
22 Figure 3. NDMI variation across 800–2000 m buffers reflecting
23 surface moisture conditions around delhi metro stations

24 2.3 Analytical Framework

25 This study employs an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS)
26 regression framework to quantify the statistical association
27 amid metro crowding intensity and localized thermal
28 conditions. The modeling approach is executed
29 independently across three spatial zones 0–500 m,
30 500–800 m, and 800–2000 m to account for spatial
31 variation in crowding effects with increasing distance
32 from metro stations. The main objective of the regression
33 is for evaluating the extent to which station-level
34 crowding, as captured by the Crowding Contribution
35 Index, influences Land Surface Temperature, while
36 controlling for the moderating ecological conditions
37 proxied by the NDVI and the NDMI. These environmental
38 variables are well-established in urban heat island
39 research for their respective cooling effects via shading,
40 evapotranspiration, and latent heat exchange.
41

42
43 Figure 1. LST variation in 800–2000 m buffer zones reflecting heat
44 patterns along the delhi metro network

45 The generic form of the regression model for each TOD
46 buffer zone is specified as:

$$47 \quad 48 \quad 49 \quad 50 \quad LST_z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot CCI + \beta_2 \cdot NDVI_z + \beta_3 \cdot NDMI_z + \epsilon$$

51 Where:

52 LST_z is the mean land surface temperature (°C)
53 observed within the buffer zone z;

54 CCI is the Crowding Contribution Index, capturing the
55 link-level impact of station-induced crowding;

56 NDVI_z and NDMI_z are zone-specific vegetation and
57 moisture indices, respectively;

58 β₀ is the intercept, and β₁, β₂, β₃ are estimated regression
59 coefficients;

60 ε denotes the error term.

61 This regression structure enables a zone-wise estimation of
62 how crowding-related anthropogenic stress and
63

64
65 Figure 2. NDVI patterns across 800–2000 m buffers highlighting
66 vegetation density around delhi metro stations

environmental conditions interact to influence LST patterns. By applying the model separately to each zone, the study captures the spatial gradients of transit-induced thermal impacts and evaluates whether crowding effects are concentrated, dissipated, or neutralized at varying distances from transit nodes.

3. Results and Analysis

To evaluate the effect of station-level crowding on localized thermal settings, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression models were estimated separately for three buffer zones surrounding each metro station: 0–500 m (core TOD), 500–800 m (transition TOD), and 800–2000 m (non-TOD). The models incorporated the CCI as the main explanatory variable, alongside ecological moderators NDVI and NDMI captured within corresponding spatial extents. No multicollinearity threshold was found.

Table 1. Linear regression for 0–500 m buffer

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Selection				
Intercept	46.2418	0.1835	251.992	< 2e-16 ***
CCI	8.4148	3.7300	2.256	0.0251 *
NDVI	-9.1565	1.4423	-6.348	1.22e-09 ***
NDMI	-12.9212	1.9220	-6.723	1.50e-10 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
 Residual standard error: 0.5117 on 221 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.7475, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7441
 F-statistic: 218.1 on 3 and 221 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

In the 0–500 m buffer zone, the model demonstrates strong explanatory power, with all predictors statistically significant. CCI exhibits a positive and significant association with Land Surface Temperature, implying that higher levels of crowding near metro stations are linked to elevated thermal conditions. This supports the hypothesis that intensified anthropogenic activity and impervious surface concentration around transit hubs may act as localized thermal stressors. Meanwhile, NDVI and NDMI show strong negative effects on LST, affirming the mitigating roles of vegetation and surface moisture.

Table 2. Linear regression for 500-800m buffer

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Selection				
Intercept	45.7606	0.2843	160.966	< 2e-16 ***
CCI	21.6284	5.8682	3.686	0.000287 ***
NDVI	-6.3723	2.1837	-2.918	0.003886 **
NDMI	-8.5852	2.9144	-2.946	0.003567 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.8129 on 221 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.3933, Adjusted R-squared: 0.3851
 F-statistic: 47.76 on 3 and 221 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-1

The model for the 500–800 m buffer zone shows a moderate fit. CCI remains positively and significantly associated with LST, and its effect size increases compared to the core zone, suggesting that the thermal influence of station-level crowding extends into the immediate transition areas. However, the buffering role of ecological factors persists, with NDVI and NDMI both exerting statistically significant cooling effects. The comparatively lower R² indicates that additional land use or built form factors may shape LST in this intermediate zone.

Table 3. Linear regression for 800-2000m buffer

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Selection				
Intercept	45.9702	0.1793	256.386	< 2e-16 ***
CCI	4.9407	3.5683	1.385	0.168
NDVI	-5.4752	1.2590	-4.349	2.09e-05 ***
NDMI	-21.5309	1.6126	-13.352	< 2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
 Residual standard error: 0.4932 on 221 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.7855, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7826
 F-statistic: 269.8 on 3 and 221 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

In the peripheral zone (800–2000 m), the model exhibits high goodness-of-fit, though CCI is no longer a significant predictor. This suggests that the influence of crowding on thermal conditions diminishes beyond 800 m, reaffirming its spatial concentration near the metro station core and transitional areas. In contrast, NDVI and NDMI continue to exhibit strong and significant negative associations with LST, reinforcing the consistent role of ecological features in mitigating urban heat across larger spatial scales.

These findings collectively highlight the spatial heterogeneity in the crowding–LST relationship and underscore the importance of incorporating ecological buffers into transit-oriented planning. The attenuation of CCI's influence beyond 800 m emphasizes the need to target heat mitigation interventions within the immediate vicinity of high-traffic transit hubs, particularly where green and moist surface coverage is limited.

4. Discussion

This study provides empirical evidence of the spatially varying influence of metro station-level crowding on urban thermal conditions across Transit-Oriented Development zones in Delhi. In the core TOD buffer zone (0–500 m), the significant positive association between

1 CCI and LST suggests that heavily crowded metro
2 stations act as thermal hotspots. This aligns with the
3 broader urban heat island literature, where high-density
4 human activity, vehicular traffic, and impervious surface
5 buildup amplify local temperatures. The increased
6 pedestrian flows, commercial intensification, and service
7 energy demands around such hubs may contribute to
8 anthropogenic heat emissions, further reinforcing
9 thermal stress. The observed thermal amplification
10 supports recent calls to integrate heat sensitivity into
11 transit infrastructure planning. Interestingly, the
12 crowding effect intensifies in the 500–800 m transition
13 zone, where CCI exhibits an even stronger coefficient.
14 This indicates that the influence of metro-induced
15 crowding is not strictly confined to station gates but
16 likely extends into adjacent urban fabric where
17 commuting, waiting, and dispersal activities unfold. Such
18 transition zones typically contain mixed land uses
19 markets, pedestrian thoroughfares, feeder services which
20 may exacerbate the urban heat accumulation due to
21 additional anthropogenic interactions. This spillover
22 effect has been largely overlooked in prior crowding or
23 thermal studies, underscoring the novelty and spatial
24 sensitivity of the proposed CCI-based approach. Beyond
25 800 m, the crowding effect becomes statistically
26 insignificant, suggesting a localized spatial decay in the
27 thermal externalities of metro crowding. This finding has
28 important implications for planning thresholds in TOD
29 policy, supporting the rationale for differentiating
30 between core, transition, and peripheral zones in spatial
31 environmental modeling. It further suggests that land use
32 and crowding interventions should be concentrated
33 within the first 800 m for maximum impact on heat
34 mitigation.

36 The consistent and strong negative associations
37 between NDVI and NDMI with LST across all buffer
38 zones reaffirm the critical role of ecological
39 infrastructure in offsetting urban heat. Vegetation and
40 surface moisture, through shading and
41 evapotranspiration, serve as natural thermal moderators.
42 These findings are in line with prior studies that
43 emphasize the importance of ecological land covers in
44 regulating urban thermal environments [17], [18]. The
45 particularly high effect of NDMI in the outer zone (800–
46 2000 m) may reflect the presence of open or less built-up
47 areas where soil moisture levels exert stronger influence.

50 Collectively, the results reinforce the environmental
51 cost of unmitigated transit crowding and make a
52 compelling case for integrating heat-sensitive planning
53 principles into the design and operation of urban metro
54 systems. This includes expanding green infrastructure
55 within walking distances of metro stations, improving
56 station ventilation and shading, and managing peak hour
57 loads to reduce thermal externalities. Moreover, the
58 application of CCI extends the relevance of transit
59 crowding research beyond passenger discomfort or

operational performance, into the realm of environmental
externalities. This contributes a novel dimension to the
crowding literature, where prior studies [11] mostly
emphasized social and service costs. This study advances
an integrated framework linking metro crowding with
urban thermal stress using sensor-enabled transit data and
remote sensing indices. By leveraging big data analytics
and spatial modeling, it contributes to the emerging field
of intelligent transportation systems that align
environmental monitoring with passenger dynamics. The
findings underscore the potential of technologically
informed, climate-responsive transit strategies for resilient
and sustainable urban infrastructure.

5. Policy Implications

The findings from this study offer critical insights for
urban planners, transit authorities, and climate resilience
policymakers. First, the positive association between the
Crowding Contribution Index and Land Surface
Temperature in TOD zones reveals that metro stations with
high passenger loads can intensify local thermal stress.
This suggests the need for transit infrastructure planning to
go beyond operational efficiency and incorporate
environmental performance metrics, particularly within
the first 800 meters of metro catchments. To address this,
policy measures should prioritize the integration of green
buffers such as urban forestry, green roofs, and shaded
pedestrian corridors around high-volume stations. Such
interventions not only enhance thermal comfort but also
improve air quality, pedestrian safety, and station livability.
Additionally, incorporating heat-resilient materials in
station design and adopting passive cooling strategies (e.g.,
natural ventilation, reflective surfaces) could further
alleviate temperature build-up around transit nodes. The
results also call for dynamic crowd management policies,
especially during peak hours, to mitigate both service
pressure and thermal impacts. Smart scheduling, fare
incentives for off-peak travel, and real-time occupancy
data dissemination can help distribute passenger loads
more evenly across time and space.

Furthermore, the study demonstrates the utility of data-
driven indices like CCI in informing spatial planning
decisions. Transport and urban development agencies
should embed such intelligent metrics into climate impact
assessments, ensuring TOD policies are sensitive not only
to accessibility and density, but also to thermal
sustainability. Given that most Indian cities are already
experiencing intensified heatwaves and climate-induced
health risks, these insights are particularly timely for
mainstreaming climate-sensitive urban transport planning
in national and state-level policy frameworks.

6. Conclusion

This study advances the understanding of how metro-
induced passenger crowding contributes to localized

1 thermal stress within urban environments. By integrating
2 CCI with satellite-derived environmental indicators LST,
3 NDVI, NDMI, the research offers a spatially nuanced
4 analysis of the environmental implications of transit
5 operations within Transit-Oriented Development zones.
6

7 Findings indicate that crowding significantly elevates
8 LST within the 0–500m, 500-800 m radius of metro
9 stations, affirming that high-intensity transit hubs
10 function as micro heat islands, particularly in the absence
11 of adequate ecological buffers. The thermal effects of
12 crowding taper off beyond 800 m, reinforcing the critical
13 role of spatial scale in evaluating transit-induced
14 environmental stress. Meanwhile, the consistent cooling
15 effects of vegetation and surface moisture across all
16 zones reaffirm the importance of green infrastructure in
17 mitigating urban heat.
18

19 By framing metro crowding as not just a service or
20 comfort issue but also an environmental externality and
21 advances the scope of interdisciplinary study at the
22 interaction of transportation systems and urban climate
23 dynamics, It underscores the imperative for transit
24 policies that are not only mobility-enhancing but also
25 environmentally responsive, integrating spatial analytics,
26 sensor-derived data, and ecological metrics into decision-
27 making. Future research can expand this framework by
28 integrating temporal analytics, examining heat-health
29 correlations, and applying it to other high-density urban
30 contexts. Ultimately, this study underscores the
31 importance of embedding environmental intelligence
32 into transit system design, where mobility solutions are
33 not only efficient but also responsive to urban climatic
34 challenges, advancing the development of intelligent,
35 sustainable, and policy-relevant transportation systems.
36

37 7 Abbreviations

38 Abbreviation	39 Full Form
40 LST	41 Land Surface Temperature
42 TOD	43 Transit-Oriented Development
44 CCI	45 Crowding Contribution Index
46 NDVI	47 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
48 NDMI	49 Normalized Difference Moisture Index
50 GTFS	51 General Transit Feed Specification
52 AFC	53 Automated Fare Collection

54 8 Statements and Declarations

55 **Competing Interests:** The authors declare that they have
56 no known competing financial interests or personal
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60 9 References

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54 contributions to sustainable and innovative transportation
55 systems and urban planning methodologies.